

A Quiet River

River is still,
still the water too.
No ripple, no current —
only quiet spread across its face.

Yet the river is still not troubled,
not bothered
by the body
that has grown a little muddy.

For within, it smiles —
it has already heard
the thundering rain upstream.

It knows what is coming.

It may carry with it
dirt and drifting mud,
but it will be enough
to cleanse my body again.

— Aditya Mishra